

ISic1317

I.Sicily inscription 1317

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object

unknown

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Carrera reports found outside the walls of the city on the west side

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, not located

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height not recorded cm

Width not recorded cm

Depth not recorded cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Θ(εοῖς) Κα(ταχθονίοις)

2. Βειψάνιο[ς]

3. Ζώτικος [ἔζησεν]

4. ἔτη · λ · Ἡρακλ[εία]

5. ἀνδρὶ εὐσεβ[εστάτῳ]

Apparatus

Text of Kaibel, with minor emendation

Kaibel: Κ[α](ταχθονίοις)

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492922

EDCS 39101687

PHI 140810

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0495 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

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Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW*. 2.11.1: 3-89. At 49

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